

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF THE FIBER-MATRIX INTERPHASE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-matrix adhesion is becoming accepted as a variable to be optimized for any composite material. The contemporary view of adhesion rests on an "interphase" model in which not only the actual chemical and physical interactions between fiber and matrix are considered but also the structure and properties of both the fiber and the matrix in the region near the interface. Although our understanding of this "interphase" is far from complete, the studies completed to date provide some insight into selection of surface treatments and finishes for certain classes of constituents. The optimum design methodology starts with the specification of the fiber and matrix from a structural consideration. Once the constituents are selected, the focus is on the creation of a beneficial fiber-matrix "interphase". This region where the fiber and matrix interact has to be designed for both "processing" and "performance". Although no quantitative algorithm is available for interphase optimization, various thermodynamic principles coupled with recently acquired experimental data can be used to qualitatively design the interphase. This includes selection of surface treatments for surface structural and chemical modification; the use of surface finishes and/or sizes to insure thorough wetting and protection of the fiber; creation of interphases with desirable stiffness, toughness and failure modes; and adhesion levels compatible with the structural environment and constituent materials.

KEYWORDS: adhesion; interface; interphase; design methodology; fiber/matrix;

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber-matrix adhesion is viewed as a necessary criterion for achieving acceptable composite properties. The patent literature contains numerous chemical formulations, processes and procedures designed to increase fiber-matrix adhesion levels so that acceptable composite mechanical properties could be achieved. As our understanding of the relationship of fiber-matrix adhesion to composite mechanical properties has increased¹, it has become

apparent that adhesion not only is necessary but if properly designed, can enhance the composite mechanical properties and performance.

Although our quantitative understanding of the fiber-matrix interface and the mechanisms of adhesion is not completely understood at this time, it is possible however to optimize the design of a fiber-matrix interphase in much the same manner as composite design methodologies are optimized. The key to success in this endeavor is using the concept of a fiber-matrix interphase as a framework upon which to build this methodology.

2. THE FIBER-MATRIX INTERPHASE

The literature is full of proposed models of adhesion, but none are effective in predicting the type of fiber surface treatment required for a given fiber-matrix combination or coupling the degree of adhesion to observed composite properties. The major reason for this lack of theoretical development lies in the oversimplification of the composition and nature of the fiber-matrix interface. Attention has been focussed on single mechanisms which were proposed to be solely responsible for fiber-matrix adhesion. Much attention has been given to the surface chemical aspect of adhesion to the neglect of other related changes that occur in the regions adjacent to the actual fiber-matrix interface. Attempts at explaining adhesion by chemical forces, electrostatic interactions, surface energetic considerations, etc. have been largely unsuccessful. A review of the models proposed compared against the growing experimental evidence that a region different in structure and composition exists near the fiber-matrix interface has lead to a reexamination of the role of surface and interfacial aspects of adhesion. The interrelationships between fiber, interface and matrix actually create a complex region (the interphase) not easily amenable to predictive analysis².

The concept of a two-dimensional interface between fiber and matrix has given way to the evolution of a three-dimensional region more properly termed an interphase. Figure 1 is a schematic representation of an interphase illustrating some of the possible components.

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of the fiber-matrix interphase indicating its three dimensional nature, the events influencing its formation and the environments in which it must function.

This interphase includes the two dimensional region of contact between fiber and matrix (the interface) but also incorporates a region of some finite thickness extending on both sides of the interface. The boundaries are defined as extending from the point in the matrix where the local properties start to change from the bulk properties in the direction of the interface. This region includes matrix that may have chemical and morphological features different from the bulk matrix. It can include impurities, unreacted polymer components, non-polymerized matrix additives, etc. At the interface, not only can there be chemical and physical

interactions between fiber and matrix, but also voids, adsorbed gases and surface chemical groups. On the reinforcement side, morphological and chemical features can be different from the bulk. Imposed upon the interphase are the processing conditions which allow chemical reactions, volumetric changes and stresses to be generated as well as the operational environment consisting of the mechanical stresses in a combined thermal and chemical environment. The resultant "interphase" can be a very complex material which does not easily lend itself to analysis by single parameter models.

Even though it is not yet possible to either quantify or predict the formation of this "interphase" from first principles, it can serve as a framework on which the interactions between composite constituents can be studied and the interphase can be designed in an optimal manner.

3. CONSTITUENTS AND SURFACE TREATMENTS

Any design methodology for composite structural applications will start with the definition of the stresses that the structural element will experience in its operational environment. In addition the thermal and chemical (i.e moisture) environments must be specified. This in turn dictates the fiber and matrix constituents to be used in the composite. The design of the interphase will change depending on the matrix (e.g. thermoset or thermoplastic) as well as the reinforcing fiber (e.g. glass, carbon or polymeric). Each constituent has different but related requirements for the interphase from both a processing and performance perspective.

3.1 Fiber Surface Treatments. In almost all cases the reinforcing fiber is never used as it is manufactured but undergoes some chemical and/or physical treatment. There are many purposes for these treatments and the type and degree differ according to the reinforcing fiber and matrix.

3.1.1 Glass Fibers. For example, in glass fibers, the native fiber surface is mainly an inorganic oxide. This surface quickly adsorbs water which creates a hydroxylated surface. If exposure to moisture is continued, the adsorption of water corrodes the fiber surface creating critical sized flaws which reduce fiber strength. This corrosion process can vary in intensity depending on the glass fiber composition. In all cases however, the glass surface must be protected from the chemical attack of water. Organo-functional silanes were produced for this purpose and have been shown to be very effective in reducing or eliminating corrosive attack of the glass surface³. Silane molecules having three hydrolyzable groups and one organic group capable of reacting with the matrix are usually applied to the glass surface. The silanol groups react with surface hydroxyls forming a siloxane bond which is very stable and not attacked by water. Recently other classes of chemicals (titanates, zirconates, etc.) have been introduced which can function in a similar manner.

This simplified model although easy to understand belies the complexity of interactions taking place when the treated fiber and the matrix are brought together. Most commercial glass fiber treatments are formulated "sizes" which contain a silane or similar molecule but blended in a solution with a film former, anti-static agent, lubricant or other ingredients in a proprietary formulation and applied to the fiber surface in thicknesses of about 0.1 μ m. The formulation is empirically designed to be compatible with the matrix used with the glass fiber. In addition to providing corrosion protection to the fiber, the "sizing" surface treatments provide protection for the fiber surface during handling operations to prevent surface damage; insure compatibility with the matrix; and aid in the infiltration of the matrix into the fiber tows during processing.

3.1.2 Carbon Fibers. Carbon fibers do not have a reactive surface in the same sense as glass fiber surfaces. The basal plane of graphite which forms the majority of the carbon fiber surface is very stable and unreactive. The edges and corners of these planes and of the resulting crystallites are the sites at which chemical reactions can take place. The

percentage of reactive edge area varies directly with the fiber modulus. For the intermediate modulus fibers used in the largest number of applications, only 20% of the fiber surface contains surface chemical groups (mostly oxygen) that can be reacted with other molecules under most conditions⁴. Attempts to increase the surface functional group content usually result in a loss of strength since the oxidation of carbon fibers invariably creates flaws which are greater than the critical size. Surface chemical treatments are used to treat carbon fiber surfaces however, but for another purpose. They etch away the native fiber surface formed during the carbonization and graphitization of the fiber. This in itself creates a surface which can withstand much higher shear loadings and therefore is largely responsible for the increase in adhesion seen with chemical surface treatments⁵. Attempts at elucidating the amount of chemical reaction between fiber surface and matrix have shown that only a few percent of these groups react with the matrix⁶.

Surface "finishes" are commonly used with surface chemical treatments for carbon fibers. These "finishes" are much simpler than "sizings" for glass fibers. Finishes are usually a matrix component applied from solvent to the fiber surface to create a layer about 0.1 μm in thickness. Since the composition is the same as the matrix, wetting and impregnation of the fiber tow is enhanced; the carbon fiber surface is protected from damage during handling; the fiber chemical reactivity is protected until processing; and the tow can be used with textile processing equipment with a minimum of difficulty⁷.

3.1.3 Polymeric Fibers. Reinforcing fibers made from polymers have surfaces which are low in energy and require some surface treatment to enhance their wettability. The polymeric fiber surface is for the most part unreactive and the use of coupling agents is generally not effective. Finishes can be used but are viewed as "processing aids" which enhance the impregnation and infiltration of the tow. Polymeric fiber surfaces are not as sensitive as the surfaces of glass or carbon fibers to abrasion and the use of a finish does not add to its protection. Likewise, corrosion is not an issue with polymers and the absorption of moisture is generally small. The application of a finish could reduce moisture pickup however. Chemical treatments, corona treatments, radio frequency discharge, microwave plasma, etc. are all used to alter the native polymeric reinforcing fiber surface. The resulting reported enhancement in adhesion is almost invariably due to removal of low energy contaminants from the fiber surface coupled with the addition of surface chemical species which improve the "wettability". Indeed, it has been shown that in the case of aramid fibers (and probably for all highly oriented polymeric reinforcing fibers) the upper limit in fiber-matrix adhesion is related to the intrinsic inter-fibrillar strength of the fiber itself in its surface layer⁸.

4. INTERPHASE DESIGN FOR PROCESSING

While the surface treatments may appear to be fiber specific, they are important from a composite processing viewpoint. One of the keys to obtaining effective composite properties is getting thorough infiltration of the fiber tow by the matrix. This infiltration process is limited by the interfacial thermodynamics. Wettability of the fiber by the matrix is taken as a necessary prerequisite for the formation of any composite material⁹. Often microscopic examination of the fracture surfaces of composite materials shows bare reinforcement surfaces and/or the presence of voids is taken as an indication that "good wetting" has not occurred. Often poor off-axis mechanical properties are attributed to less than ideal fiber-matrix adhesion which is somehow related to poor wetting. There is a linkage between fiber surface chemistry, matrix surface free energy, thermodynamic wetting of the fiber by the matrix and adhesion of the matrix to the fiber. The generation of adhesion during composite processing is a dynamic event which can be affected by processing conditions and which ultimately can affect composite properties.

4.1 Equilibrium Thermodynamics of Surface and Interfaces. Thermodynamics provides an excellent framework upon which to study the surface of the fiber and matrix and to quantify the interactions which can occur when they are brought together. For small molecule liquids where the time constants for the rearrangement of molecules is short, equilibrium thermodynamic relationships are available which describe the interactions between the solid surface and the liquid phase which can be used to understand and predict polymer matrix interaction with the reinforcing fiber¹⁰.

4.1.1 Surface Free Energy. An atom or molecule on the surface of a liquid or a solid has a net force acting on it pulling it toward the interior of that phase. The manifestation of this force is commonly called the surface tension. In a liquid where the rearrangement of molecules takes place on the microsecond scale, the surface tension can be observed creating a "skin" on the liquid. Liquids that are composed of molecules that exert dispersion forces alone (e.g. hexane) have low values of surface tension and liquids with a highly polar nature (e.g. water) have large values of the surface tension. Solids have a surface free energy also but since the atoms in the surface can not rearrange spontaneously like in a liquid, its surface appears to be unaffected by any disturbance.

4.1.2 Contact Angle. When a liquid having a surface tension τ_{LV} is placed on a solid surface with surface tension τ_{SV} , the liquid will spontaneously form a droplet or spread out into a film. If a droplet is formed a relationship between the solid surface tension and the liquid surface tension can be derived if the surface tension are considered to be vectors acting at the edge of the drop.

Figure 2. A schematic diagram of the contact angle and the surface tension forces which determine its equilibrium value. The equations relate the polar and dispersive free energies of the solid surface to the contacting phase.

The surface free energy of the solid-liquid interface is labelled τ_{LS} and the equilibrium can be expressed as

$$\gamma_{LV} = \gamma_{LS} + \gamma_{LV} \cos \theta$$

where θ is the angle formed by the drop surface with the solid surface measured through the liquid. Various established physical chemical methods are available for measuring the surface tension of a liquid and optical methods and gravimetric methods are available for measuring the angle which the droplet makes with the solid surface. Neither the solid surface tension nor the solid-liquid interfacial tension can be measured directly but the difference between the two is the product of the cosine of the contact angle and the liquid surface tension.

Liquids that form contact angles greater than 90° are called "non-wetting". Liquids that form a contact angle less than 90° are termed "wetting". If the liquid does not form a droplet, i.e. the contact angle is 0° , the liquid is said to be "spreading" and the relationship does not hold. The equilibrium is expressed by an inequality where

$$\gamma_{SV} - \gamma_{LS} \geq \gamma_{LV}$$

because as the liquid flows it is decreasing the solid-vapor interface. Closer inspection of this relationship leads to the conclusion that for all cases of wetting and spreading, the surface tension of the wetting liquid must be greater than the solid surface tension.

A term frequently used is the Work of Adhesion (W_A), which gives an expression for the thermodynamic work necessary to create a solid-vapor surface and a liquid-vapor surface by pulling apart the solid-liquid interface.

$$W_A = \gamma_{LV} + \gamma_{SV} - \gamma_{LS}$$

By substituting the equilibrium expression for the droplet forming the contact angle the work of adhesion is given by

$$W_A = \gamma_{LV}(1 + \cos\theta)$$

This expression is a thermodynamic work and as such is a reversible, equilibrium value. Likewise it is not to be confused with the work of disrupting an adhesively bonded interface between reinforcing fiber and matrix which includes many substantial energy absorbing and dissipative processes. This thermodynamic expression actually states that the maximum value of the work of adhesion occurs when the contact angle is equal to zero and the work of adhesion is twice the surface tension of the liquid.

Although these expressions apply to equilibrium situations they can be used to understand the wetting process in a polymer-reinforcement systems as well. For example, Sharpe has shown that even in highly viscous polymer melts, the interfacial tension is the controlling factor. In a very simple yet elegant experiment polyethylene which has a low surface tension but is very viscous was melted and placed on the surface of an epoxy specimen. Adhesion was very high. When the liquid epoxy was placed on solid polyethylene however, the adhesion was very low even though the viscosity of the liquid epoxy was very low illustrating controlling role that surface energies have over liquid viscosity. True thermodynamic equilibrium may never be attained especially for the high viscosity thermoplastic matrix composites.

Zisman used these concepts to identify a critical solid surface tension for polymers. He noted that if the cosine of the contact angle was plotted against the contacting liquid surface tension, a straight line would result which intersected the 0° line at some value of the surface tension. By testing a variety of polymer surfaces, he found that there was a characteristic value for τ_c , which was an intrinsic characteristic of the solid. If a liquid had a surface tension greater than τ_c , the liquid would form a droplet on the surface and if it was less it would spread on the surface. This concept reinforced the rule that for spreading to occur, the surface tension of the liquid had to be less than that of the solid.

Kaelble¹¹ built upon some earlier work of Fowkes and proposed that the surface tension or more properly the surface free energy of a liquid or a solid is composed of dispersion interactions and higher order ones such as polar interactions. If liquids with known dispersion and polar components of their surface free energy were used as contacting fluids with solid surfaces, the polar and dispersive components of the solid could be determined. This resulted in an expression for the work of adhesion which was related to the contact angle and the liquid surface free energy which could be measured directly through the following expression. Where the surface tensions refer to the dispersive (D) and polar (P) components of the solid (SV) and liquid (LV) phases.

A plot of the left hand side of this equation versus the ratio of the square roots of the polar to dispersive ratios of the contacting liquids results in a straight line whose intercept

whose slope and intercept determine the dispersive and polar component of the surface free energy of the solid.

$$\frac{\gamma_{LV}(1+\cos\theta)}{2\gamma_{LV}^{D/2}} = \gamma_{SV}^{D/2} + \frac{\gamma_{LV}^{P/2}\gamma_{SV}^{P/2}}{\gamma_{LV}^{D/2}}$$

Although the discussions on wettability have focussed on the thermodynamics between the fiber surface and the matrix, real composite systems are very large assemblies of small diameter fibers. A key to creating good composite properties is infiltration of the matrix into this fiber assembly or "tow" during the processing steps. The small interstices in the tow can create very large capillary forces which aid in the wetting process. This capillary force is commonly characterized as a pressure drop due to the surface tension acting in the small capillaries. A relation quantifying this driving force for infiltration is where the height of the

$$\Delta P - \Delta \rho gh = \frac{\gamma_{LV}\cos\theta}{2r}$$

rise of a liquid of density rho, is directly related to the liquid surface tension τ_{LV} , the cosine of the contact angle θ and inversely related to the radius of the capillary. The contact angle controls the capillary forces since at $\theta=90^\circ$, the capillary force vanishes and at $\theta>90^\circ$ prevents infiltration.

The thermodynamic analysis of wetting and capillarity is true for equilibrium conditions. Thermoplastic polymer melts or thermoset polymer mixtures are high viscosity fluids which may never reach true thermodynamic equilibrium during the processing of a composite. Yet the condition predicted by the analysis is valid. That is, the surface tension of the fiber must be greater than that of the matrix. A properly designed interphase should employ surface chemical treatments, finishes and/or sizings which enhance the composite processing to minimize the contact angle between matrix and reinforcement to gain the most assistance from capillary forces during composite processing. This will insure displacement of any moisture and assist the transport of voids from the composite during processing.

5. INTERPHASE DESIGN FOR PERFORMANCE

If the interphase is considered to have some finite size, it plays a role in the mechanical performance of the composite. At a minimal level, the interphase structure is responsible for the level of adhesion which insures continuity in the transfer of forces from fiber to matrix, allowing the composite to function as one mechanical entity. The interphase also acts as a failure site when a fiber fails. Either interfacial or matrix failure can result. It is tempting to extrapolate that high levels of adhesion are the most desirable condition for the composite and that a high degree of chemical bonding is the best way to achieve this condition. This is not the case and there is a practical limit to the adhesion level that can be produced in any fiber-matrix system.

If a stress analysis is conducted on a single isolated fiber in the matrix, an expression for the local shear stress similar to one attributable to Cox¹² can be derived. Closer inspection of the terms shows that there are fiber dependent terms, geometric terms related to the fiber geometry and position, and matrix dependent terms. If the "interphase" is considered to exist as a component of the composite near the fiber surface, its mechanical properties limit the degree of adhesion. A recently published study¹³ where single fiber methods were used to measure fiber-matrix adhesion was conducted in which the same matrix chemistry was used but with polymers having different distances between crosslinks and therefore different mechanical properties. The interfacial interactions that result in the formation of the "interphase" were constant but the resulting "interphase" mechanical properties were changed. The fiber-matrix interfacial shear strength also changed with interphase composition. Figure

Figure 3. A plot of the interfacial shear strength versus the matrix properties for a carbon fiber/epoxy system showing the dependence on the matrix properties alone.

3 shows that the adhesion varied as the product of the square root of the matrix shear modulus. This indicates that when fiber surface treatments affect the resulting structure of the polymer in the interphase, when the surface finishes produce an interphase different in modulus from the bulk, or when the surface "sizings" create an interphase with a modulus different from the bulk matrix, it is the interphase properties and not the bulk properties that determine the level of adhesion.

In a similar manner, the fracture properties of the composite are controlled by the interphase structure and properties. Recent results¹⁴ have shown that fiber-matrix adhesion affects both fiber off-axis and on-axis composite properties. At low levels of adhesion, interfacial failure is the predominant mode. As the adhesion is increased interfacial failure continues to occur up to a point where matrix failure becomes the dominant failure mode (Figure 4). Matrix failure reduces composite toughness and in fiber dominated tests also

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of these interfacial failure modes which can be induced by altering the level of fiber-matrix adhesion.

reduces the maximum level of properties that can be expected from the composite. This is true for tensile and shear. However, for compression, transverse tension and flexure, the matrix failure mode does not take place and composite properties increase with increasing

Figure 5. Plots of the composite shear strength and composite transverse flexural strength for the same carbon fiber/epoxy system with three levels of adhesion and three different failure modes.

levels of fiber-matrix adhesion (Figure 5). Therefore, the fiber-matrix interphase has to be selected to produce the "optimum" level of adhesion for the predominant design load.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Using the concept of a fiber-matrix "interphase", a qualitative design strategy can be used to optimize the fiber-matrix interphase. It should consist of the following sequence.

First, after specification of the constituents, surface treatments (chemical, finishes or sizings) are selected depending on the fiber and matrix. The surface treatments reduce fiber sensitivity to handling damage; protect the fiber surface reactivity; remove undesirable contaminants; alter fiber surface chemistry; change fiber surface morphology; and promote compatibility with the composite matrix.

Second, surface treatments are selected in order to optimize and be compatible with the processing procedures. Thermodynamic compatibility of the fiber-matrix interface must be achieved by minimization of the interfacial free energy. This will insure complete and thorough wetting of the fiber and displacement of any moisture or voids during processing.

Third, surface treatments are selected with the objective of creating desirable mechanical properties in the interphase. No single mechanical parameter characteristic of the fiber-matrix interphase can be used as the design goal, rather the highest level of adhesion consistent with interfacial failure and not matrix failure will insure an optimum combination of composite mechanical properties and performance. A focus on maximum adhesion alone is not desirable. The intrinsic material limitations of the matrix in the interphase and mechanical strength of the fiber surface may be a limiting factor in the ability to design the optimum interphase.

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